

Influence of solvent on preparation of silica nanosphere

N. Venkatathri

Department of Chemistry, Anna University, Chennai-600 025, India

E-mail : venkatathrin@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 14 November 2007, revised 5 May 2008, accepted 16 July 2008

Abstract : Normally silica nanospheres were synthesized using ethanol as solvent. The draw back in this method is the result of non-uniform particle size. Octadecyltrimethoxy silane was used to normalize it. As it is costly, there is need for alternative method. Here in this communication we changed the solvent to acetone, isopropanol, *n*-octanol, etc. We succeed in getting a monotype nano silica particle when we used these three solvents. Even though the experiment is simple, the impact is more. It is found that the density of the solvent plays an important role in particle growth. There is an optimum value of density, above or below which precipitate was not produced.

Keywords : Silica, nanosphere, solvent, density.

Introduction

Amorphous silicate nanoparticles are used in many applications including ceramics, catalysis, pharmaceutical, electronic packaging and chemical-mechanical polish¹⁻⁵. In particular, special attention has recently been paid to methods for controlling the nanospheres, size and distribution, because they exhibit peculiar and desirable properties in the wafer polishing process. Monodisperse silica nanospheres were first synthesized by Stober *et al.* using sol-gel method which induces high purity in the resulting particles⁶. Bogush and Zukoski reported the influence of reaction parameters such as ammonia and water contents on the particle size and distribution⁷.

Recently silica nanospheres have been considered effective candidates for chemical-mechanical polishing materials. so several investigators have reported to control particle size by using reactor type and varying the concentrations of ammonia, water and alcohol solvent⁸⁻¹⁰. They also examined the influence of reaction method (such as semi-batch reaction and batch reaction) on particle size and distribution. A relatively slow rate of hydrolysis of TEOS occurred during the semi-batch process, which resulted in larger silica particles and a narrower size distribution⁹.

This paper describes a study on influence of different solvent on synthesis of silica nanosphere. The solvents having different density and polarity¹¹ were used.

Experimental

Synthesis of silica nanosphere using ammonia catalyst and ethanol solvent was carried out as follows : 3.14 ml of aqueous ammonia (28–30%, Aldrich, USA) was added to a solution containing 74 ml of ethanol (99%, Aldrich, USA) and 10 ml of deionized water. Eleven milliliters of tetraethoxysilane (TEOS, 98%, Aldrich, USA) was added to the above prepared mixture at 298 K with vigorous stirring and the reaction mixture $11.4\text{SiO}_2 : 6\text{NH}_4\text{OH} : 149\text{H}_2\text{O} : 297.5\text{EtOH}$ was stirred continuously for 2 h to yield uniform silica spheres. The silica nanosphere was retrieved by centrifugation and further calcined at 823 K for 6 h under an air atmosphere to produce the final solid. With the same molar ratio, different solvent containing reactions were carried out. The results are listed in Table 1.

The particle size and shape were analyzed by a Topcon, SM-300 scanning electron microscope. The copper disc pasted with carbon tape and the sample was dispersed over the tape. The disc was coated with gold in ionization chamber.

Table 1. Effect of solvent on hard core mesoporous silica shell formation with ammonia as catalyst

Sl. No.	Solvent	Density (g/mL at 25 °C)	Polarity	Yield (%)	Growth period (h)	Particle size	Particle shape
1.	Isopropanol	0.785	3.9	58	2	450 nm	Spherical
2.	Ethanol	0.789	5.2	77	2	200–400 nm	Spherical
3.	Acetone	0.791	5.1	46	2	500 nm	Spherical
4.	Octan-1-ol	0.827	4.0	67	2	150 nm	Spherical
5.	<i>n</i> -Hexane	0.659	0	–	2–24	–	–
6.	Cyclohexane	0.779	0.2	–	2–24	–	–
7.	Water	1.000	9.0	–	2–24	–	–
8.	Propylene glycol	1.036	–	–	2–24	–	–
9.	Ethylene glycol	1.113	–	–	2–24	–	–

Results and discussion

Solvent play a media role in particle growth. Polarity and density¹¹ of the solvent are playing important role. *n*-Hexane, cyclohexane, water, acetone, isopropanol, ethylene glycol, propylene glycol, octan-1-ol, were used apart from ethanol (Table 1). Yields follow parabolic behavior with respect to density. With polarity the time required to particle growth decreases. The SEM photograph of the samples is given in Fig. 1. All solvents give spherical particles in nanoscale with particle sizes ranging from 100 to 450 nm. Except octan-1-ol all other solvents give similar (450 nm) particle size and shape. *n*-Hexane, cyclohexane, propylene glycol, ethylene glycol did not give precipitate, which may be due to excess and lower from

optimum density (0.785 g/mL to 0.827 g/mL). Similarly, polarity also have an optimum range (3.9 to 5.2). There is similarity between the optimum range of catalyst and solvent density (Table 1). However, the basicity and polarity are not related. It is reported that with solvent polarity the nanosphere particle size are decreased. Polarity is measured in terms of dielectric constant. However, in our experiment we found that it is almost constant except for octan-1-ol.

Conclusion :

Silica nanosphere was synthesized by a novel different solvents method. The influence of nature of solvent on synthesis was studied. Density of the solvents plays an important role in particle growth. An optimum range of density is required to precipitate silica. Above and lower to which no precipitate is formed.

Acknowledgement

The author N.V. thanks Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for a fellowship.

References

1. R. K. Iler, "The Chemistry of Silica", Wiley, New York, 1979.
2. M. D. Sacks and T. Y. Tseng, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1984, **67**, 526.
3. R. Masuda, W. Takahashi and M. Ishii, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 1990, **121**, 389.
4. M. Yamashita, Demiya H. Mori and T. Maekawa, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.*, 1992, **100**, 1444.
5. M. Taira and M. Yamaki, *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Med.*, 1995, **6**, 197.

Fig. 1. SEM pictures of samples synthesized from different solvents : (a) ethanol, (b) octan-1-ol, (c) acetone and (d) isopropanol.

Note

6. W. Stober, A. Fink and E. Bohn, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1968, **26**, 62.
7. G. H. Bogush and C. F. Zukoski, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 1988, **104**, 95.
8. S. K. Park, K. D. Kim and H. T. Kim, *Colloids Surfaces A : Physicochem. Eng. Aspects*, 2002, **197**, 7.
9. K. D. Kim and H. T. Kim, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Tech.*, 2002, **25**, 183.
10. S. Sadasivan, D. H. Rasmussen, F. P. Chen and R. K. Kannabiran, *Colloids Surfaces A : Physicochem. Eng. Aspects*, 1998, **132**, 45.
11. Aldrich (2005-2006), Aldrich Chemical Company, New York, USA.